

POTENTIAL FOR IMPROVEMENT IN A REFINERY'S STEAM NETWORK OPERATIONAL STABILITY

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Abstract

The topology and operation of a steam network in a large industry is influenced by its past development to a great extent; the same holding true for the SLOVNAFT refinery. Along with commissioning of new conversion technologies, introduction of energy saving measures and shutdown of obsolete units the core of steam production shifts from the Central combined heat and power unit to the local steam sources producing steam from hot waste heat streams. Dimensions of steam pipelines that served the steam transport demand well in the past gradually become either too large or too small, causing the steam to locally cool down and condense or to stream with high velocities. Both cases negatively influence the steam network operation and put more strain on its proper management and its future development projects. Starting from actual operational state analysis that is presented in another contribution, calculations were performed to model future steam network operation. This is anticipated to be seriously influenced by commissioning of new technologies in near future and several proposals have been formulated to ease their impact on its stability. Combined effects of new production units commissioning and the proposed measures were tested in order to select the most promising proposals for further elaboration. The presented results should serve the energy management to prepare action list where considering future investments aimed at steam network evolution.

Introduction

In practice there is a lot of evidence on the utility networks mathematical modelling. By optimizing the back-pressure/condensing turbines operation and steam imports in a German refinery, the system achieved average 2.75 mil. USD/year¹ cost savings. The rigorous Utopia model covers all process units and the entire steam system. As such, it is useful for data reconciliation, steam balancing, marginal steam value calculation and "what if" studies preparation. Due to unusual complexity of the steam system, rigorous simulation is unsuitable for daily use, instead of it a simpler optimizer (Exopt) has been created. This was designed to extract only the essential information from large data set and it deals only with turbine modelling, basic steam balancing, operating cost calculation and flow sheet optimization (open loop operation). Experience shows that by continuously "fine-tuning" the operations using Exopt, an additional 550 000 USD/year of benefits can be achieved. In another petrochemical plant with steam network at different pressure levels with several equipment: heaters, strippers, steam turbines and let down valves, which operates co-generation plant to produce steam and electricity, steam production and consumption optimization program was done. With proper mathematical modelling, which optimized the plant steam balance (minimize let downs, steam venting, calculate equipment operation effectiveness) a total of 24 t/h steam consumption saving was achieved (2 % of total steam generation)². Few years later, by extension of the optimization model they managed to achieve additional savings of potential of economy of 46 t/h high pressure steam generation in boilers and reduction of 6 MW in electric power consumption, which means almost 5 % of total steam generation savings³. The authors conclude that the most challenging part of their work was the steam model. These examples and other results support the importance of proposed work. As it turns out, these issues didn't become actual in recent years, but they have been a problem for decades and undoubtedly we will also have to deal with them in the future.

As it was mentioned previously, for steam network optimization and stabilization, functional and reliable mathematical model is a must. It should be able to describe different systems at various operational states. In general, the more complex the mathematical model is, the more accurate results it provides. Thanks to progress in science and technology, our possibilities nowadays are almost unlimited. On the other hand, there are costs and difficulty of use increasing with model's complexity. One should always start with the simplest one and continuously increase the level until needed, but not more⁴. One of the models proposed in the past is based on the laws of conservation of mass and energy and although solving differential equations is needed, the calculation algorithm is relatively simple⁵. This model was applied in the case of single pipe as well as complex

pipe network in Chinese steel plant. Reliable results with relative errors of few % only were obtained in both cases.

Complicated energy networks are typical for large industrial plants like SLOVNAFT oil refinery and our attention is paid mainly to steam networks. With three interconnected steam pressure levels (HPS – high pressure steam, MPS – middle pressure steam, LPS – low pressure steam) with total length of few tens kilometres each, the entire network represents a dense mash of pipes. Management of such large pipeline system is not a simple task and operators often have to deal with different operational problems. Their goal is to ensure the operational stability of the network in order to avoid undesirable technological problems and also unnecessary increase in the operational costs. Not just steam networks, but the entire plant goes through various changes that come with new technologies or new production process demands. These changes may affect every part of the plant and the nature of production in a serious way. The SLOVNAFT refinery finished an energy conservation program involving several production units focused on energy and yield improvement and has started to focus also more on production and processing of polymers in recent years, which influences final product portfolio also in the refinery part. As the plant evolved with oil and gas industry development (emerged new production facilities in the refinery), the current operational parameters of the steam networks totally different than they were designed for 40 to 50 years ago. Nowadays there are few problematical sections, because they are oversized, leading to excessive steam condensation, or undersized, leading to increased pressure drops. Such problems can be solved easily by replacing those sections for ones with appropriate dimensions suitable for the current operational state, but it is very expensive. In addition, as mentioned, the whole plant evolves constantly and there are few projects proposed for the future that will definitely affect whole plant operation as well as the stability of steam network.

Simulation

Proposed work is dedicated to modelling the operational state of steam networks after commissioning of proposed projects within the SLOVNAFT refinery in following years. They are:

- A. Connecting C6 and S2 units in the HPS network by common pipeline (since 2018)
- B. New SWAATS unit for sulphur fertilizers startup (since 2018)
- C. New hydrogen production plant startup thus replacing the old one (since 2020)

Each of these projects will cause certain changes within the steam network. Proposals concerning topology only (case A) have no effect on the total mass balance but it does not apply for proposals concerning production units (cases B and C). Connection of units C6 and S2 by common pipeline is actually at the preparation stage. There is also a new production unit SWAATS in the construction stage, which will process part of the “sour gases”, thus reducing the load of the S2 unit and solving the problem with the already insufficient capacity of S2 unit. As a result, HPS production at S2 unit will drop by more than 11 t/h. Moreover a steadily increasing content of sulfur in crude oil could be processed and a reserve will be created in terms of S2 unit production capacity. SWAATS unit will be located near the S2 unit. Currently there is a new hydrogen production plant HPP3 in the design stage, but it is supposed to replace already existing but obsolete hydrogen plant S1 and should join the pipeline in its proximity. In this case the HPS supply would be increased from the current amount of 11 t/h up to 35 t/h. These changes will undoubtedly affect whole HPS network. If operational states of all other production units remain unchanged, the amount of HPS supplied from CHP unit will need to be modified in order to retain the total mass balance of the HPS network. Therefore the steam flow through individual pipe segments also will be changed. The impacts of proposed investments on each steam pressure level’s mass balance is clearly illustrated in the Table I.

Table I

The impact of proposed investments on the amount of steam exported to steam network

Steam pressure level	Steam export change [t/h]		
	A	B	C
HPS	-	-11.6	+25.0
MPS	-	+7.3	-
LPS	-	-	-9.2

Proposed work uses the same mathematical models as were used for analysis of steam network’s current operational state. The first one is a simple Balance model created in MS Excel, which is only used for mass and heat balances as well as steam flow velocities calculations. The second one is Hydrodynamical model created in

a commercially available software, which allows hydrodynamic calculations or heat transfer calculations with ease and offers new possibilities. The simulation schemes for both models were modified according to information from SLOVNAFT refinery employees to capture the real location of new units. The advantage of both models is simple modifiability so this was not a difficult task. Except changes of simulation schemes it was necessary to just slightly modify the balance equations and enter some input parameters for calculations. A part of modified calculation schemes is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Segment of simplified HPS simulation scheme including proposed changes (existing interconnection of major steam pipelines = dot-dashed line, new steam pipeline = dashed line)

The purpose of simulations was to determine the way the steam flow in pipelines will be affected after implementation of proposed changes. Specifically values of temperature and pressure at units acting as steam consumers were monitored. As expected, the closest units to the place of proposed changes will be affected the most. For the needs of simulations, an operational data corresponding to a standard operational state without any unit shutdown was selected. The operational state of steam network also depends on different operational states of some production units throughout the year as well. Such evidence is Figure 2 showing an amount of HPS supplied from CHP unit in year 2017.

Figure 2. The amount of HPS supplied from CHP unit to the steam network

In proposed work simulations were done with data representing winter, summer and intermediate weather conditions. Specific values of model parameters are listed in Table II together with steam amounts supplied to HPS network confirming various steam network's operational state. From the view of steam network management and plant dispatching it is important to secure a stable operational state under all circumstances.

Table II
Selected model parameters and HPS amounts supplied to steam network

	Date, time [-]	Outside temperature ⁶ [°C]	Wind speed ⁷ [m/s]	HPS export from CHP unit [t/h]	Total HPS supplied to steam network [t/h]
Winter	3.1.2017, 10:00	-5	2	53.18	112.30
Intermediate	22.4.2017, 6:00	10	3	60.93	101.13
Summer	10.7.2017, 19:00	30	3	28.07	97.67

Simulations were done with two values of thermal conductivity of thermal insulation. The value of $\lambda_i=0.038 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ corresponds to new thermal insulation in a proper technical state. On the other hand, the value of $\lambda_i=0.08 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ corresponds to real state of thermal insulation and it was determined on the basis of the results of our previous work dealing with the analysis of HPS network's current operational state. Another important parameter is the insulation thickness. The standard value used in SLOVNAFT refinery is $\delta_i=120 \text{ mm}$. Simulations were performed for variations of proposed projects as well as change A separately and results were analysed. In all cases, the simulations were performed in a way that kept the HPS network balanced, therefore, it was necessary to modify the amount of HPS supplied from CHP unit.

Results and discussion

The Hydrodynamical model was used for simulations of proposed projects within the HPS network to determine the final effect on the network's operational state. Besides temperature changes at each production units, the effect of season was examined. According to SLOVNAFT refinery designers group, permanent operation of a pipeline connecting the production units C6 and S2 located at ends of main pipelines and thus creating a circuit should resolve the problem of relatively low steam temperature at the C6 unit. The steam temperature at its battery limit is typically in a range of values from 295 to 310 °C. Naturally, one would expect higher heat losses during the winter months, which was also confirmed by results of simulations showing lower temperature at C6 unit. Therefore the next part deals with the results of simulations performed for winter conditions as this was the worst case and the results are slightly better in other seasons. In the time corresponding to simulation data, the average measured steam temperature at C6 unit was 301.9 °C and temperatures obtained by simulations after implementation of proposed changes are listed in Table III.

Table III
Results of simulations for winter conditions and the value of thermal conductivity of thermal insulation of $\lambda_i=0.08 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$

Scenario	T [°C]					
	C6	C5	C4	C7	C8	C9
Present	308.8	300.0	288.6	316.8	311.4	313.7
A	292.9	302.5	291.1	331.1	325.8	328.1
A+B	292.9	305.2	337.4	335.3	329.8	332.2
A+C	293.7	330.4	317.2	315.4	310.4	312.6
A+B+C	295.8	330.4	317.2	315.0	310.1	312.2
B+C	308.8	315.3	303.4	319.9	314.3	316.7

The results show, that in the case A separately, the steam temperature at C6 unit will drop by more than 15 °C in case of a bad technical state of thermal insulation of pipes. The simulation results for proper thermal insulation are listed in Table IV. In this case, the already significant temperature drop increased up to 20 °C. Since the steam

temperature is already too low, it would bring the quality closer to its saturation point and thus enhancing the risk of condensation.

Table IV

Results of simulations for winter conditions and the value of thermal conductivity of thermal insulation of $\lambda_i=0.038 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$

Scenario	T [°C]					
	C6	C5	C4	C7	C8	C9
Present	316.8	303.1	297.2	322.9	320.1	321.3
A	296.4	306.1	300.3	336.1	333.5	334.7
A+B	296.4	312.9	351.1	339.5	336.8	338.0
A+C	296.7	331.8	325.2	320.3	317.8	318.9
A+B+C	300.4	331.8	325.2	320.9	318.4	319.5
B+C	316.8	317.6	311.4	323.9	321.2	322.4

Based on these and other results, following statements concerning C6 unit can be formulated:

- The connection of units C6 and S2 itself would not help to increase the steam temperature at C6 unit and it would be not suitable for permanent operation. As a result, a significant temperature drop would be observed.
- Commissioning the SWAATS unit would most likely also not improve the quality of steam at C6 unit, because even though decreased load of S2 unit, the steam would flow to C6 unit due to its high pressure. Such loads of HPS supplied from S2 unit are affected by heat losses just slightly and won't change its quality fundamentally.
- The operation of HPP3 unit would improve the steam temperature at C6 unit just slightly. The reason is also high steam pressure at S2 unit, which would cause the steam from HPP3 unit flow mainly in the opposite direction.
- After implementation of change C in summer conditions, it would not be possible to reduce the steam supply from the CHP unit into the network, because it would go beyond the possible minimum. In this case a circuit on the C major pipeline needs to be opened to allow the HPS to flow back to the CHP unit and maintain the steam flow. It is also possible to start operating steam turbines that are shut down due to their low effectivity at the moment. Possibly further proposals out of scope leading to operational state adjustment may be invoked (replacement of an obsolete steam turbine at S2 unit, etc.).
- The real situation could be even worse because the measured steam temperature at C6 unit is few centigrade lower than the temperature predicted by model in current operational state. The difference in winter conditions is 6.9 °C while in the summer, it is only 4.1 °C.

As mentioned before, all units connected to HPS steam network will be affected by proposed measures even if there are no problems concerning low steam pressure. Results estimate a steam temperature increase at C4 unit and C5 unit, which is the second closest to the S2 unit after C6 unit. A significant temperature increase at units C7, C8, C9 in case A and A+B can be explained by steam supply drop from S2 unit. Smaller amount of a relatively cold steam from S2 unit will flow through the F major pipeline and interconnection of major steam pipelines and on the other hand, these units will be supplied by steam of good quality from the S4 unit. In this case, there will be also higher volume of steam supplied from the CHP unit with very high temperature over 360 °C. Simulations expect slight temperature decrease in case of HPP3 unit operation, however this difference is negligible. This fact can be explained as follows. The amount of steam supplied from CHP unit will be much smaller and even if the temperature of steam from HPP3 unit will be relatively high, its transport through a long pipe section to get to mentioned production units would cause great heat losses.

Following previous statements, it is recommended to abort the project A as it would not meet its original intentions. For that reason, another simulation for the scenario of commissioning changes B+C only was done. According to the results of simulation, the steam temperature at C6 unit will not increase but at least it will not worsen. In addition to it, all other units listed in Table 3 and Table 4 will observe a temperature increase.

Simulations concerning new hydrogen production plant were performed for operational state planned for such load, that will replace already existing hydrogen production plant in terms of the amount of the hydrogen produced. However, this unit's goal is also to achieve higher load for future hydrogen consumption increase of the refinery and steam supply up to 54 t/h HPS at its full load is expected. This means that the amount of steam

supplied from this unit could change in a moderate way in the future according to its operational state, which will have significant impact of the HPS network again.

Results of previous work dealing with analysis of current operational state of the HPS network confirm, that the measured data corresponds very well with the calculated data and the Hydrodynamical model provides reliable results. Relative errors of temperature values are typically under 5 %, bigger errors are considered to be caused by incorrect measurement. In terms of steam pressure, there aren't any important changes observed. Pressure gradient is the steam flow direction determining factor. In case of the connection of units C6 and S2, pressure drop of 5 kPa is predicted by the model and compared to the absolute pressure value of HPS, it is negligible value. This pressure drop at this section is comparable to the pressure drops anywhere else within the HPS network. One can conclude that if pressure ratios remain unchanged, the steam will flow in the direction from S2 unit to C6 and not the opposite way. The operation of HPP3 unit could have a significant impact on the steam network operation, because a large amount of steam with high pressure will be supplied. Its pressure will be comparable to the pressure of steam from S2 unit and it will be interesting to watch the final operational state after implementation of proposed changes, because the mathematical model could not assess these influences. The future objective is to use another simulation tool that is able to determine the steam flow distribution in each pipe segment by pressure ratios. The simulation scheme is prepared, but due to significant complexity and IT limitations, successful solution was not yet obtained.

Conclusions

Proposed work uses mathematical modelling to review the impact of planned changes on SLOVNAFT refinery's HPS network operation and operational stability. Some of proposed projects have specific goal to improve the HPS network's operation. It should be pointed out, that proposal A is designed to increase the steam temperature at C6 unit, which is typically in the range from 295 to 310 °C and is being transported through a long pipe section from S3 unit nowadays. From this point of view, the results claim that constructing the connection of units C6 and S2 is meaningless, because the final effect will be exactly the opposite of the expectation and the temperature will decrease even more. This definitely is not desired goal as it enhances the risk of steam condensation in the connecting and adjacent pipelines. As the primary intention was an alternative route for steam export, the only positive is the possibility to put it into operation only during pipeline maintenance works on the F major pipeline between units S2 and S1, but it will be too luxury due to high capital costs. This would mean that this pipeline would be operated only in ON/OFF mode. Even if it's not the goal, the influence of other projects to HPS network cannot be avoided. The paradox is, as shown by the results, that these changes may increase the steam temperature at other production units even if there aren't any problems with its quality observed. The best solution would be to abort the project A thus not worsening the steam quality at C6 unit and improving its temperature at all other units instead. According to our SLOVNAFT refinery supervisor, this project is in too advanced state to do so.

Proposed work proves the advantage of mathematical models since it is possible to assess the impact of proposed measures on steam network's operation even before their realisation and without physical interventions in the construction. The same approach will be used onwards for other pressure level networks. Based on results, it is possible to assess whether desired effect will be reached and make decisions on the next procedure or modifications of the proposal. This way unfavourable proposals can be excluded in advance and the most suitable solutions can be found.

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